

Aminophenols and Phenylenediamines as Corrosion Inhibitors for 70/30 Brass in Nitric Acid

M. N. DESAI, B. C. THAKER and P. M. CHHAYA

Chemistry Department University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9

Manuscript received 17 July 1974; revised 10 May 1975; accepted 19 May 1975

Aminophenols and phenylenediamines are reported as inhibitors for the corrosion of 70/30 brass in nitric acid. The relative order of protectivity is ortho > meta > para. All the substances are cathodic in nature and act by reacting with nitrous acid, thus breaking the autocatalytic cycle of nitrous acid formation.

NITRIC acid is highly corrosive to copper and its alloys. If suitable inhibitors are found, nitric acid can be used for cleaning surfaces of copper and its alloys. The present paper describes the behaviour of aminophenols and phenylenediamines as corrosion inhibitors for 70/30 brass in nitric acid solutions.

Experimental

Cold rolled, 70/30 brass quarter hard temper supplied by Messers Kamani metals was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were as described in our earlier publication¹.

Fig. 1. Effect of current density on cathode and anode potentials of 60/40 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors.
●—● Blank (2.0N nitric acid)
○—○ *o*-Aminophenol (0.2%)
▲—▲ *m*-Aminophenol (0.2%)
△—△ *p*-Aminophenol (0.2%)

Fig. 2. Effect of current density on cathode and anode potentials of 60/40 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors.
●—● Blank (2.0N nitric acid)
○—○ *o*-Phenylenediamine (0.2%)
△—△ *m*-Phenylenediamine (0.2%)
▲—▲ *p*-Phenylenediamine (0.2%)

The influence of inhibitor concentration on inhibitor efficiency is given in Table 1. The effect of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 2N HNO₃ in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in Figures 1 and 2.

Observations

In general, at low concentrations all the phenylenediamines accelerate the corrosion of 70/30 brass in nitric acid solutions.

In 2N and 3N nitric acid, the effective inhibitive concentration of *o*-phenylenediamine, is 0.05%, but in 4.0N nitric acid higher concentration (>0.2%) is needed.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION ON INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY

Inhibitor concentration	2.0N Nitric Acid (120 Min)		3.0N Nitric Acid (60 Min)		4.0N Nitric Acid (30 Min)	
	Loss Mg/dm ²	%Efficiency	Loss Mg/dm ²	%Efficiency	Loss Mg/dm ²	%Efficiency
Nil	1893	—	9152	—	9264	—
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine						
0.01%	2923	-54	8039	12	*	
0.05%	28	98	36	99	*	
0.1 %	28	98	13	99	*	
0.2 %	28	98	12	99	6.6	99
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine						
0.01%	376	80	7593	17	10375	-12
0.05%	40	98	1707	81	10318	-11
0.1 %	31	98	3195	97	9107	2
0.2 %	30	98	163	98	577	94
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine						
0.01%	2143	-12	10533	-15	12213	-32
0.05%	1534	19	10916	-19	12916	-39
0.1 %	52	97	10173	-11	13726	-48
0.2 %	43	98	1314	85	14100	-52
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol						
0.01%	1668	12	7303	20	9815	-6
0.05%	492	78	6703	27	9049	2
0.1 %	396	80	59	99	1012	96
0.2 %	376	80	50	99	38	99
<i>m</i> -Aminophenol						
0.01%	1235	35	6482	29	9634	-4
0.05%	205	88	5991	34	9264	0
0.1 %	132	93	221	97	9101	2
0.2 %	128	93	165	98	27	99
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol						
0.01%	1474	22	6525	29	8969	3
0.05%	1361	28	6470	29	9128	1
0.1 %	98	95	6207	32	9488	-2
0.2 %	98	95	1721	81	10300	-8

* The metal specimen dissolves completely in 4.0N HNO₃

In the case *m*-isomer, the effective concentrations in 2, 3, & 4.0 N nitric acid are respectively 0.05%, 0.1%, and 0.2% *p*-Phenylenediamine is not at all useful in 4.0 N nitric acid. Even in 3.0N nitric acid its efficiency is not good. Of the three phenylenediamines, ortho isomer is the best inhibitor. At 0.2% concentrations of ortho and meta phenylenediamines 70/30 brass is protected to an extent of 99% for the periods of study.

In all the three aminophenols, the effective inhibitor concentration is 0.2%. At 0.2% concentration, ortho and meta aminophenols give 98-99% protection to 70/30 brass in 3 and 4N nitric acid. But do not give adequate protection in 2N nitric acid. However with *p*-aminophenol, the protectivity decreases with an increase in nitric acid concentration and in 4N HNO₃, it accelerates the corrosion of 70/30 brass. In 2N nitric acid, the efficiency of amino phenols improves with time, whereas in 3 N nitric acid, it is nearly constant for the durations of study. With all these inhibitors, the potential values with time are more negative than those in 2.0N nitric acid alone indicating probably the predominant action of these inhibitors on local cathodes.

All the three phenylenediamines increase both the cathode and anode polarisations, the former to a significant extent. With ortho and para phenylenediamines, the corrosion is accelerated at 0.01% concentration. Polarisation measurements in 2N nitric acid containing

0.01% ortho and para phenylenediamine confirm this behaviour. Shifts in cathode potential during cathode polarisation at this concentration are less than those in 2N nitric acid containing no inhibitor.

With meta and para aminophenols, both the cathode and anode are polarised, the former to a much greater extent. In the presence of 0.2% *o*-aminophenol, shifts in cathode potential during cathode polarisation are less than those in 2.0N nitric acid without inhibitor, which indicates that the cathode reaction is facilitated in the presence of the inhibitor. It is likely that due to the facilitation of the local cathodic reaction, the potential shifts in the passive region and inhibition is achieved. In such a situation, the compromise potential in the presence of the inhibitor must have shifted in the positive direction, considering that the corrosion of brass in HNO₃ is cathodically controlled. Actually, the compromise potential shifts in the negative direction in the presence of the inhibitor. This may be due to the shift of the open circuit potentials of the local cathodes and/or anodes in the presence of the inhibitor.

Dezincification

The results obtained with studies in dezincification of 70/30 brass in 2.0N nitric acid are given in Table 2. The theoretical ratio of Cu/Zn for 70/30 brass is 2.333. In 2.0N to 4.0 N nitric acid, there is dezincification of 70/30 brass. In 2.0N to 4.0N solutions of nitric acid,

TABLE 2
Ratio of Copper/Zinc in Nitric
Acid for an Immersion Period of

Inhibitor and (inhibitor concentration)	2.0N	3.0N	4.0N
	HNO ₃ (120 min)	HNO ₃ (60 min)	HNO ₃ (30 min)
Nil	1.95	1.7	1.50
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine (0.2%)	0.76	0.82	—
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine (0.2%)	2.06	2.11	2.14
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine (0.2%)	1.91	1.76	—
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol (0.2%)	2.1	1.9	1.4
<i>m</i> -Aminophenol (0.2%)	1.9	1.34	1.16
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol (0.2%)	1.6	1.27	1.15

0.2% *m*-phenylenediamine suppresses the dezincification of 70/30 brass. In 2.0N HNO₃, 0.2% *o*-aminophenol

suppresses dezincification. The remaining substances enhance the dezincification of 70/30 brass which is particularly evident with *o*-phenylenediamine. It is well-known that the corrosive attack of nitric acid on copper-zinc alloys is due to the autocatalytic formation of nitrous acid. The amino phenols and phenylenediamines act as inhibitors by reacting with the nitrous acid and the formation of diazo compounds. Moreover, these amino inhibitors in acidic medium give rise to onium ions which may be adsorbed over the local cathodes.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the University Grants Commission for the award of research fellowship to P. M. C. and B. C. T.

References

1. M. N. DESAI and S. M. DESAI, Second Symposium on Corrosion Inhibitors, Ferrara, 1965, 863.